

Duration of untreated psychosis and its correlation of cognitive decline in patient with Schizophrenia – A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background:

The Duration of untreated psychosis (DUP) signifies the interval between the onset of initial psychotic symptoms and the commencement of appropriate antipsychotic treatment. The complexity of underlying psychopathology, characterized by nonspecific prodromal symptoms, overlapping manifestations with other psychiatric disorders, denial of illness, and insidious onset, often leads to delays in treatment initiation.

Case Presentation:

Mr. R, a 34-year-old unmarried male from a rural background in Salem, was brought to medical attention in March 2023 by his mother and a neighbour. His mother reported a change in his behaviour over the past decade, characterized by wandering, self-conversations with his deceased father, increased anger outbursts, neglect of personal hygiene, public acts of urination and defecation. Despite treatment with antipsychotics and Electroconvulsive therapy (ECT), his cognitive function remained impaired, with moderate to severe cognitive deficits persisting.

Conclusion:

Mr. R 's case highlights initial symptoms including wandering, hallucinatory behaviour, and disorganized conduct, leading to poor social and occupational functioning. In conclusion, DUP potential negative impact on cognitive function.

Keywords: Duration of untreated Psychosis, Cognitive Function, Electroconvulsive therapy.

Background: A Duration of untreated psychosis is defined as time from appearance of first psychotic symptom to initiation of adequate antipsychotic treatment .^(1,2)

The underlying psychopathology, including non specificity of the prodromal symptoms, considerable overlap of the prodromal symptoms with other psychiatric disorders, denial of illness, and insidious onset, may delay the initiation of treatment.^(1,2,3)

It has been hypothesized that prolonged duration of untreated psychosis may lead to worsening of the neurodegenerative process that is implicated in the pathophysiology of schizophrenia and to poor clinical outcome.^(1,2,4)

Cognitive deficits constitute core features of schizophrenia, encompassing general intellectual deficits and more specific deficits, such as processing speed and working memory. These deficits occur in verbal and nonverbal cognitive domains in premorbid prodromal, first-episode, chronic, and remitted stages of illness.⁽¹⁰⁾

They are independently associated with functional outcomes, which supports the view that schizophrenia is a neurodevelopmental cognitive disorder. Less is known about the trajectory of cognitive deficits after the development of psychosis.⁽¹⁰⁾

Cognitive differences that occur between the prodrome stage and the conversion to schizophrenia are usually small and restricted to a few cognitive domains.⁽¹⁰⁾

Case Presentation:

Mr. R 34years old unmarried male, studied 12th standard belonging to lower socioeconomic status came from rural background in salem, Patient was brought by his mother and neighbour friend on march 2023, Patient's mother complained that patient was apparently normal 10 years back following which patient's mother noticed that patient would walk around the house, talking to self and when asked about it he would replies that he was talking to his father who is dead. mother also noticed that patient had increased anger outburst which was unproved and he was constantly fighting with his family members and was using obscene words. Patient was stopped going to work and was not taking care of family ,previously he used to go for work regularly and takes care of family. mother noticed that patient was not taking bath and wore the same clothes and did not groom himself that is not his usual self, During this time mother noticed that his appetite was as usual. Patient was also noticed to urinate and defecate in public and would not clean afterward. one day mother noticed that patient was missing from the house following which a search was launched and police complaint was filed. he returned back to home by himself after 2 years following which patient's mother that he had more rubber bands in left arm and left wrist ,so they took him into government hospital in locality where first aid was given and advised for surgery ,patient was absconded from the hospital following his mother and neighbours couldn't locate then they filed complain again after a year he came to home by himself and started to roam around his hometown during that time patient's mother and neighbours noticed that he stays in roadside and comes home sometimes to have food and roaming in outside, he also urinates and defecates in public place and doesn't maintains self care and hygiene.

On admission Patient was started on T.Risperidone 4mg and was increased into 10mg over period of 2 months, Along with this patient was started on T.Haloperidol 5mg and increased into 10mg over a period of 2months.on Mental Status Examination it was noticed that impaired attention and concentration, immediate and remote memory was impaired, not adequate intelligence according to his social, occupational and educational background, concrete thinking ,impaired judgement and poor insight. Mini Mental Status Examination was done and found to have score of 12 indicating moderate to severe cognitive impairment.

Patient's condition did not improve even on adequate trial of antipsychotics following which Electroconvulsive therapy was started and patient underwent 5 successful session of ECT, following which 20% improvement in his behaviour, self care and patient was discharged on request with Long acting injection Haloperidol decanoate 50mg and T. Risperidone 10mg, During follow up Patient was maintains self care, not started to go for work stating the reason of his unfunctional limb, no wondering behaviour, hallucinatory behaviour was noted by his mother, but patients attention concentration, immediate and remote memory, intelligence, abstract thinking was impaired, poor insight, personal and social judgement was partly intact, Mini Mental Status Examination was done and found to have score of 14 which indicating moderate to severe cognitive impairment, no much improvement in cognitive function.

Conclusion: Patient initial presentation of wandering away from home, behaviour suggestive of hallucination, disorganised behaviour ,poor social occupational functioning. Longitudinal studies have shown that a prolonged period of untreated psychosis in the first episode of schizophrenia is associated with unfavourable illness outcomes in regard to severity of symptoms, number of hospitalizations, remission and relapse rates, social and cognitive functioning, and response to treatment. ^(1,4)

Further, a ten-year follow-up study of 109 cases of first-episode psychosis has reported that neurological-like symptoms at onset of illness predict poor long-term outcomes. ^(1,8)

Some data suggest that inevitable clinical deterioration as a result of long duration of untreated psychosis is consistent with worsening of the neuropathological process of schizophrenia . ^(1,9)

This is evidenced by reduction of the cortical (mainly frontal) volume and enlargement of the cortical sulci at baseline as measured by brain neuroimaging studies. ^(1,9)

The untreated psychosis is associated with progressively lower performance on a battery of cognitive tests. This finding differs from shorter-term studies of the duration of untreated psychosis, which generally report unchanging impairment of cognitive function or short-term cognitive decrease and no association between the duration of untreated psychosis and cognition. ⁽¹⁰⁾

In conclusion, evidence suggests an association between prolonged duration of untreated psychosis in the first episode of schizophrenia and poor prognosis. It is hereby noticed that duration of untreated psychosis might have negative impact on cognitive function of the patient.

List of Abbreviations:

- 1) DUP - Duration of untreated psychosis
- 2) ECT - Electroconvulsive therapy

Declarations

- **Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate:**
 - Not applicable
- **Consent for publication: Applicable**
 - Obtained Consent from the Individual included in my study
- **Competing Interests:**
 - I declare that we have no competing interests
- **Funding:**
 - No grants or funding
- **Acknowledgement :**
 - Not applicable

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